

Adsorption of maltose at the solution-alumina interface

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The adsorption of maltose from its aqueous solution performed onto the alumina surface at constant pH 6.0 and temperature $30 \pm 0.2^\circ$ obeys the Langmuir model. Various adsorption, kinetic and thermodynamic parameters have been calculated. The adsorption is significantly affected by pH of the suspension, presence of salts and organic solvents in the medium and temperature of the system. The adsorption is confirmed to be of physical type in nature.

A large number of technological and biological applications have been investigated to the simple phenomenon of adsorption¹. However, rather less work has been done on the adsorption behaviour of carbohydrates. In the present study, the adsorption of maltose has been investigated at the solution-alumina interface.

Results and Discussion

Concentration effect and adsorption isotherm : To observe the effect of maltose solution on its adsorption varying concentrations ($2.9\text{--}20.4 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm⁻³) were used. It was found that the adsorption increases with increasing maltose concentration and finally levels off. The isotherm appears to belong to L2 type and thus the adsorption process follows the Langmuir scheme². The adsorption coefficient (K) calculated from the linearized Langmuir equation³ was found to be 2.41×10^2 dm³ mol⁻¹. This value is much higher than that obtained in the case of glucose adsorption⁴, indicating a greater adsorption of maltose onto alumina than glucose.

Kinetics : It is recognized that the progress of adsorption is a two-regime process.^{5,6} At the initial stages, the substrate surface is bare and the kinetics of adsorption is governed by diffusion of the molecules from bulk to the surface. All the molecules that arrive at the surface are assumed to be immediately adsorbed. The mass transport can be interpreted as a Fickian diffusion. In a simple model calculation the diffusion coefficient (D) is obtained from the slope of the curve drawn between the adsorbed mass $q(t)$ as a function of \sqrt{t} which depends on the bulk concentration,

$$q(t) = \frac{2C_0}{\sqrt{\pi}} \sqrt{Dt} \quad (1)$$

From the slope of the curve $q(t)$ as a function of \sqrt{t} , the diffusion constant D can be calculated. In the later stages, a

barrier of adsorbed molecules exists and the molecules arriving from solution have to diffuse across this barrier. This penetration is slow and a theoretical treatment given by Ligorue and Leibler⁵ predicts an exponential time-dependence for the later stages,

$$q(t) = q_{\text{eq}} [1 - \exp(-t/T)] \quad (2)$$

where q_{eq} is the adsorbed amount at equilibrium and $1/T$ is called as the penetration rate constant.

The progress of the adsorption process has been monitored by knowing the amounts of adsorbed maltose at different time intervals. The results reveal that the rate of adsorption is almost constant up to 40 min and then decreases exponentially with time and finally attains a limiting value near 90 min. Thus in the constant rate-region the kinetic scheme of Bajpai and Bajpai⁷ can be applied to evaluate the rate constant for adsorption (k_1) and desorption (k_2). Also, from eqns. (1) and (2) the diffusion constants (D) and penetration rate constant ($1/T$) can be calculated. These kinetics parameters for 0.06×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ maltose concentration have been calculated: k_1 , 32.5×10^4 s⁻¹; k_2 , 13.5×10^6 s⁻¹; D , 2.7×10^{11} cm² s⁻¹; $1/T$, 6.2×10^4 s⁻¹. This clearly implies from the numerical values of k_1 and k_2 that the rate of adsorption is 200 times more than that of desorption.

Because of the nonionic nature of maltose, its adsorption onto alumina was supposed to be of physical in nature and it was confirmed also by performing desorption experiments of adsorbed maltose. The desorption experiments, in which about 90% maltose was recovered from the maltose-adsorbed alumina, clearly indicates that the weaker type of binding forces are involved in adsorption of maltose onto alumina. A variety of functional groups are present in the maltose molecule and mainly H-bonding should be involved as the binding forces. Since the adsorption experiments were done

at pH 6.0, the surface of alumina must bear a positive charge due to $-AlOH_2^+$ type of groups. These interactive forces operate between maltose molecules and alumina surface.

pH effect : In all ionic systems⁸ the effect of pH has a direct influence on the adsorption behaviour of solutes. In the present study since the adsorbate is nonpolar and the surface is polar in nature, the effect of variation in pH of the suspension will hardly affect the charge profile of the carbohydrate. However, a remarkable change in charges over the alumina surface definitely occurs and as a consequence the adsorbed amount will be affected.

In the present study the effect of pH variation (2.8–11.7) on the adsorption of maltose has been studied. The results indicate a rise in the adsorption with increasing pH and then follows a decrease beyond the pH 9.0. At the experimental pH 6.0, which is quite below the isoelectric point of alumina (9.0)⁹, the alumina surface will have a net positive charge owing to the presence of $-AlOH$ and $-AlOH_2^+$ groups on its surface. At this pH the partially negatively charged oxygen of the OH group in the maltose molecules is held with the positively charged surface. Now, upon increasing the pH, the surface acquires decreasing positive charges and therefore the electrostatic attraction between the maltose molecule and alumina surface increases. This increase continues up to pH 9.0 which is the isoelectric point of alumina and where the adsorption reaches a maximum. Various kinetic parameters of the adsorption process have also been calculated (Table 1). The kinetic data also supports our experimental findings. For instance, the data imply that the rate constant for adsorption has the largest value at isoelectric point of the alumina (9.0), at which a maximum adsorption is noticed. Also, the largest value of diffusion constant at pH 9.0 reveals that the maltose molecules diffuse much readily across the interface at this pH and get adsorbed on the alumina surface. However, beyond this pH the alumina surface acquires a negative charge due to AlO^- groups. Now at this stage an electrostatic repulsion starts acting between the oxygens of the AlO^- and OH groups of the alumina surface and maltose molecules respectively.

Table 1. Kinetic parameters for the adsorption of maltose on to alumina at various pH

pH	k_1 $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$	k_2 $\times 10^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$	D $\times 10^{11} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$1/T$ $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$
2.8	10.75	4.42	2.70	6.2
4.0	15.17	6.27	2.85	4.1
7.0	16.28	6.73	3.13	3.6
9.2	18.83	7.79	3.43	4.8
11.7	16.75	6.93	1.08	6.0

Salt effect : Low molecular weight ionic compounds affect the adsorption kinetics appreciably. In ionic system, the addition of ions causes a change in charge profiles of the adsorbate and adsorbent thus altering the magnitude of binding forces in the system, and as a consequence, the adsorption is affected¹⁰.

In the present investigation, the effects of addition of anions on the amounts of adsorbed maltose have been studied by adding sodium salts of the respective anions in the concentration range 0.01–0.10 M. Plots representing the variation of the adsorbed amount with ionic strength of the medium are shown in Fig. 1 which imply that the adsorption increases with increasing added salt concentrations and decreasing charge of the anions. The effectiveness of the added salts follow the sequence, $Cl^- > SO_4^{2-} > PO_4^{3-}$. Similarly the cations were added in the same concentration range as anions and the adsorption was found to decrease in the sequence, $Na^+ < Ca^{2+} < Al^{3+}$.

The results may be attributed to the following facts. (i) In the case of addition of salts, the added anions cause screening of the repulsive force operating between the maltose molecules and the positively charged aluminols of the surface and thus the adsorption increases. This also reveals that the adsorption should increase with the increasing anion charges and, therefore, the PO_4^{3-} ion should be the most effective one. However, a reverse sequence of effectiveness is observed which may be explained by the fact that because of the bulkier dimensions of the SO_4^{2-} and PO_4^{3-} ions the maltose molecules arriving at interface experience steric hindrance with the bi- and trivalent anions and thus the adsorption does not increase as much as that in

Fig. 1. Plots showing the effect of anion concentration on the adsorbed amount of maltose at fixed maltose concentration ($0.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$).

the case of Cl^- ions. However, due to the screening effect produced by the sulphate and phosphate ions the adsorption increases. Thus, it reveals from this reasoning that a multiple charged anion should produce a lesser adsorption and this has been found true. (ii) In the case of added cations a decrease in the adsorbed amount has been observed which is quite obvious as in the presence of cations the electrostatic repulsion between the maltose molecules and the positively charged aluminols of the surface increases which, in turn, results in a fall in the adsorbed amount. The whole mechanism of decreased adsorption in case of cations has been modeled.

For a fixed concentration of salts the rate constant for the adsorption and desorption were calculated and the results are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Kinetic parameters for the adsorption of maltose on to alumina in the presence of salts

Salts	k_1 $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$	k_2 $\times 10^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$	D $\times 10^{11} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$1/T$ $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$
Cl^-	34.2	14.15	0.50	5.8
SO_4^{2-}	29.3	12.12	0.70	4.8
PO_4^{3-}	27.9	11.54	4.20	5.4
Na^+	29.6	12.25	4.90	4.8
Ca^{2+}	31.4	12.29	4.30	4.4
Al^{3+}	35.8	14.81	3.90	5.0

Solvent effect : Solvents have profound effect on the adsorption of substances as the addition of a solvent to an aqueous medium significantly affects the solvent quality of the medium. Moreover, certain physical properties such as the dielectric constant, surface tension, cohesive energy density of solvents also exert a direct impact on the solute-surface interaction.

In this investigation, the effect of aliphatic alcohols on the adsorption of maltose has been observed by adding the respective alcohols to the adsorption medium. It was found that in the presence of alcohols the adsorption increased and obeyed the following sequence: $\text{H}_2\text{O} < \text{MeOH} < \text{EtOH} < \text{iso-PrOH} < \text{n-BuOH}$. The following explanation may be given to justify the obtained results. (i) Since the adsorption follows a Langmuir model, a competitive adsorption exists between the maltose and the solvent molecules for the interface. As butanol has the bulkiest molecule than the others, its adsorption on the surface will be less than the other alcohols and thus the maltose molecules will be adsorbed in greater amounts with n-BuOH in comparison to other alcohols. Since the order of bulkiness of the alcohol molecules follows the sequence, $\text{MeOH} < \text{EtOH} < \text{iso-PrOH} < \text{n-BuOH}$, the sequence obtained in effectiveness of alcohols

in adsorption is well justified. (ii) With increasing number of carbon atoms the solvent quality of the medium also decreases, resulting in a greater adsorption of maltose with n-BuOH. (iii) Another reason may be that since the dielectric constants of water and different alcohols obey the following increasing order, $\text{water} < \text{MeOH} < \text{iso-PrOH} < \text{n-BuOH}$, it is obvious that water will be the best and water-n-BuOH mixture will be the most poor solvent of maltose and, therefore, the adsorption will be maximum with n-BuOH. These findings have been further confirmed by the kinetic data as summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Kinetic parameters for the adsorption of maltose on to alumina in the presence of solvents

Solvent	k_1 $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$	k_2 $\times 10^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$	D $\times 10^{11} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$1/T$ $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$
Methanol	9.0	3.72	0.66	4.5
Ethanol	9.8	4.05	1.45	5.8
Propanol	10.5	4.34	3.02	5.5
Butanol	11.2	4.63	2.67	5.2

Temperature effect : Temperature has a direct influence on the amount of the adsorbed substance. In the present investigation, the adsorption experiments were performed in the temperature range 5–45° and the results indicate that the adsorption of maltose decreases with increasing temperature of the medium (Fig. 2). The results may be explained due to the following reasons. (i) With increasing temperature the binding forces between the surface and maltose molecules are weakened and the adsorption decreases. (ii) At lower temperature physical agglomeration of maltose molecules may not be ruled out¹¹. The proposed agglomeration of maltose molecules has been further confirmed by large viscosity of the maltose solution at lower temperature

Fig. 2. Effect of temperature on the adsorbed amount of maltose (mg g^{-1}).

: 1.1091 at 5°; 0.0098 poise at 25°. Obviously, due to agglomeration the adsorption is supposed to increase. (iii) At higher temperature the escaping tendency of maltose molecules from surface to the bulk will be greater and thus the adsorption is less.

In several cases an increase in the adsorption at higher temperature has also been reported¹² and explained by the fact that at higher temperature the number of active sites increases on the surface. However, this was not observed in the present case.

Several thermodynamic parameters have also been calculated : ΔG° , $-4.67 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$; ΔH° , $-6.69 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$; ΔS° , -6.7 cal g-mol . The negative value of entropy suggests that as the adsorption proceeds the maltose molecules arrange orderly at the interface and this obviously appears also.

Experimental

Maltose (Loba) aqueous solution was of pH 6.0. The alumina (B.D.H.) had a specific surface area of $18.0 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ as determined by BET measurements. All solutions were prepared in double-distilled water and other reagents used were also of A.R. grade.

Viscosity measurements were carried out with an Ostwald type viscometer.

Method : Adsorption experiments were carried out as described earlier¹³. In brief, a known volume of maltose solution (25 ml) containing alumina (0.2 g) at pH 6.0 was shaken for 2 h, till the equilibrium adsorption was reached. The amount of adsorbed maltose was determined by estimating the residual concentrations of maltose in the supernatants by the phenol-sulphuric acid method¹⁴. The pH of the suspension was also recorded after adsorption experiments and it was found almost constant.

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